

E-ENERGY

Brand Guidelines

www.australo.org

Table of content

Visual Tools

Logo

Colors

Typography

Mockups

Logo

Main version

E-ENERGY

Logo

Secondary versions

Colors

Introduction to the selected color palette for a brand

The brand's color scheme includes the primary, secondary, accent (or exception to use in case of an error), and neutral colors such as white or grey.

The primary color is the most dominant and recognizable color of the brand, followed by the secondary colors that complement and contrast with the primary color. The secondary colors are ordered according to the priority indicated in the diagram on the right, where the top color has higher priority than the bottom color. Refer to the diagram on the right for specific colors.

Royal Red Primary

#D80565
R216 G5 B101
C0 M98 Y53 K15

French Plum Secondary

#8E146B
R142 G20 B107
C0 M86 Y25 K44

White Neutral

#FFFFFF
R255 G255 B255
C0 M0 Y0 K0

Sunglow Secondary

#FFC533
R255 G197 B51
C0 M23 Y80 K0

Black Neutral

#000000
R0 G0 B0
C60 M40 Y40 K100

Light Coral Accent

#F98086
R249 G128 B134
C0 M49 Y46 K2

Old Lavender Texts

#846E7A
R132 G110 B122
C0 M17 Y8 K48

Colors

Specification of the gradient table

The gradient table indicates which neutral color (grey or white) to use for writing text based on the percentage of opacity.

Refer to the adjacent table for more information.

Gradient table

100%	100%	100%	100%
------	------	------	------

80%	80%	80%	80%
60%	60%	60%	60%
40%	40%	40%	40%
20%	20%	20%	20%

Typography

Title

The font displayed is intended for use only in titles and subtitles.

[Download here](#)

Kanit SemiBold

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj
Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss
Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

0123456789

[(@#%\$^&)]" <>!?

Aa

Titles

Typography

Paragraph

The font displayed on the page is intended for use in paragraphs only.

Aa Bb

[Download here](#)

Mina Regular

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj
Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss
Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

0123456789

[(@#%\$^&)]"<>!?

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat. Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exerci tation.

Mockups

E-ENERGY

Title Example

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat. Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis autem vel eum iriure dolor in hendrerit in vulputate velit esse molestie consequat, vel illum dolore eu feugiat nulla facilisis at vero eros et accumsan et iusto odio dignissim qui blandit praesent luptatum zzril delenit augue dui dolore te feugait nulla facilisi.

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat. Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat.

Title Example

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat. Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exerci tation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat.

Duis autem vel eum iriure dolor in hendrerit in vulputate velit esse molestie consequat, vel illum dolore eu feugiat nulla facilisis at vero eros et accumsan et iusto odio dignissim qui blandit praesent luptatum zzril delenit augue dui dolore te feugait nulla facilisi.

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat. Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exerci tation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat.

Title Example

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat.

Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis autem vel eum iriure dolor in hendrerit in vulputate velit esse molestie consequat, vel illum dolore eu feugiat nulla facilisis at vero eros et accumsan et iusto odio dignissim.

E-ENERGY

Brand Guidelines

www.australo.org